

LOWLAND TAPIR
CONSERVATION INITIATIVE

PROTOCOL FOR THE INDIVIDUAL IDENTIFICATION OF LOWLAND TAPIRS (*Tapirus terrestris*)

VIA CAMERA TRAPS

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1st EDITION | 2026

CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION	04
SEX	07
COAT PATTERN OF TAPIR CALVES	11
EARS	25
TAIL	33
HEAD	36
SCARS	40
OTHER CHARACTERISTICS	48
TIPS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	60
APPENDIX (RELIABILITY TABLE)	61

INTRODUCTION

Identifying tapirs using photos or videos from camera traps is a fundamental tool for the study and conservation of the species. **Recognizing each individual** allows for monitoring their presence and permanence in a given area, understanding movement patterns, estimating population size, monitoring health and reproduction, and even recording behaviors and aspects of life history that would otherwise remain unknown.

The identification of individual tapirs may seem challenging at first glance. Unlike species where adults exhibit unique patterns, such as the rosettes in jaguars, tapirs do not have individual patterns. Therefore, **more subtle markings**, such as small scars, details on the ears and tails, coat patterns derived from their juvenile pattern, and body variations can make all the difference to a trained eye in distinguishing these individuals.

However, factors including the animal's movement, the angle of image capture by the camera trap, the distance from the camera, and the amount of light can result in poor-quality records where certain details appear only partially or are completely invisible. Furthermore, most tapir sightings occur during twilight or at night, when these animals are most active, but color images can reveal other characteristics not previously perceptible in monochromatic (grayscale) records.

For these reasons, identification usually **depends on comparing several images** obtained in different situations, which allows for revealing characteristics that do not appear in a single record. It is essential to take all necessary precautions to avoid overestimating the number of individuals in a population before obtaining complete and consistent information.

This guide was developed with the aim of providing a clear, accessible, and applicable **individual photo-identification procedure for tapirs** in different regions, allowing the user to develop their own identifications (IDs) from their camera trap records.

ANATOMICAL REGIONS USED

The figure below presents the nomenclature of the **main anatomical regions** adopted in this guide, with the aim of standardizing the description and facilitating the communication of observed characteristics.

For reliable individual identification, it is recommended to use at least **three visible and distinctive characteristics**. In the following sections, the main characteristics that can be used in this process will be described, along with complementary guidelines. Included in the appendix is a table with the **degree of reliability** associated with each of these characteristics.

Images from different angles of the same individual greatly facilitate identification.

In (a), we can observe that the ear has cuts and markings. For more information about ears, go to **PAGE 25**.

In (b), we can observe the tail shape and the spots on the tail, as well as the sex and some spots on the hind leg. For more information about the tail, go to **PAGE 33**.

In (c), we can observe spots on the tail and hind legs, as well as lateral stripes, spots on the face, and small scars along the body. For more information about tapir calf spots, go to **PAGE 33**.

In (d), we can observe spots on the tail and hind legs, as well as lateral stripes, spots on the face, and small scars along the body. For more information about tapir calf spots, go to **PAGE 33**.

SEX

LEVEL OF
RELIABILITY:
HIGH

Determining the sex of the animal is one of the first steps in distinguishing individuals, as it reduces the range of possible identifications. In tapirs, sexual dimorphism is subtle, but specific anatomical characteristics allow for relatively reliable differentiation between males and females when the image or recording offers good visibility of the posterior/lower body region.

FEMALES

Female with noticeable mammary glands.

Female with slightly swollen vulva.

MALES

Scrotal sac and penis exposed.

Visible scrotal sac.

Penis exposed.

It is important to note that determining an animal's sex can be difficult when individuals are still young. The genitalia of these individuals are still developing, so they may show little anatomical differentiation between males and females, which reduces the reliability of identification at unfavorable angles.

Furthermore, lactating females may have more prominent mammary glands. Depending on body position or lighting, this characteristic can be confused with male genital structures.

Male with underdeveloped testicles.

Female's mammary glands during lactation.

Male with underdeveloped testicles.

Female's mammary glands during lactation.

COAT PATTERN OF TAPIR CALVES

Tapirs, at birth, have a coat pattern consisting of spots and stripes, with vertical and horizontal markings, whose essential function is camouflage. This pattern is **unique to each individual**. However, these markings begin to disappear during the first few months of life and disappear completely around 10-11 months of age.

Even so, in some individuals, part of their spots and stripes may remain in their adult coat, especially on the sides of the body, chest, face, legs, and even the tail.

Below, the same individual is observed on different dates, showing that the intensity of its markings **varies according to the age of the animal and the lighting conditions** at the time of image capture or recording. Notice that it is not always possible to clearly see the same spot or stripe, which does not mean that it has disappeared, but rather that it is necessary to gather records obtained from **different angles, distances, lighting conditions, and situations** to confirm the identity of the individual.

For more information on how to identify the age of a tapir calf using its spot pattern, please refer to the **“PROTOCOL FOR ESTIMATING THE AGE OF LOWLAND TAPIR (*Tapirus terrestris*) CALVES THROUGH EVALUATION OF THE SPOT PATTERN OF THEIR COAT”**.

Growth of the same individual recorded over the course of months (RIGHT side of the body).

Growth of the same individual recorded over the course of months (LEFT side of the body).

Below, we have separated, into categories, the different anatomical regions that may retain the stripes and spots of when the animal was a calf and how these can aid in the identification of individuals.

ABDOMEN

This is the easiest way to recognize an individual. Adult animals that retain their calf coat pattern on the side of their body are easily recognizable and can be tracked throughout their lives.

However, in some tapirs, the stripes may only appear under certain lighting conditions.

Examples of adult tapirs with different patterns of stripes and spots on the side of their body.

Same images as on the previous page but focusing on the stripes on the animals' coats.

LEGS

It is quite common for spots to remain on the inner part of the tapir's legs. This makes it a precise and very relevant characteristic for individual identification. However, it is important to take several **sets of images of different leg positions**. Also, notice the difference between color and monochrome photos. Try to compare when the legs are in the same anatomical position.

Same tapir individual recorded in color and monochrome photos.

Same tapir individual recorded in color and monochrome photos.

Same tapir individual recorded in color and monochrome photos.

POSTERIOR REGION OF THE PELVIS

Same individual in different positions. Notice the white markings around the anus, remnants of the animal's calf coat or a white anus.

LEVEL OF
RELIABILITY:
HIGH

In the photo on the left, lighter patches can be observed around the tail. In the photo on the right, there is a spot remaining from the animal's calf coat.

Photos of the same individual with a whitish anal region.

CHEST

Some individuals retain markings of different shapes on the lower part of the neck. This characteristic is more easily observed in color images.

Same tapir individual recorded in color and monochrome photos.

FACE

Some tapirs retain the stripes of their calf coat on their face. Observation of this anatomical region **is more challenging**, as visualization is often only possible when the animal passes very close to the camera.

EARS

The ears are one of the most informative parts of the body for identifying tapirs, as they can present cuts, tears, marks, or spots of different shapes on specific regions of the surface of the skin.

Continuous updating of records for the same individual is recommended, as **new cuts or lesions may appear** throughout its life.

Furthermore, the cuts may look slightly different **depending on the angle** from which the ear is seen.

Lastly, it is important to note that the white mark on the upper portion of the ear is a natural characteristic of the species and should not be used as an identification criterion.

Note: For better referencing and comparison of cuts and markings in different photos of the same individual, these traits will be indicated with numbers instead of arrows or circles.

LEVEL OF
RELIABILITY:
HIGH

NATURAL CUTS AND MARKINGS

Same tapir individual recorded in color and monochrome photos.

Same tapir individual recorded in color and monochrome photos.

Same individual from different angles.

Same individual from different angles.

Same individual from different angles.

MARKINGS

The white portion of the ear, on the upper part, will always be present (a). However, it will not always be present on the lower part (b), nor will the small stripe at the insertion of the dorsal surface of the ear (c).

Small white spots on the dorsal surface of the ear.

Small white stripe on the proximal part of the dorsal surface of the ear.

TAIL

The tail is one of the most relevant characteristics for individual identification, since it is highly unlikely that two individuals will have identical tails.

Its **shape, length, and width** can vary noticeably, as can the **presence, quantity, and size of spots or other markings** in this anatomical region. These variations, generally stable over time, make the tail a particularly useful element for distinguishing between tapirs.

In the two pages that follow, each letter represents a different individual, and the same individual is represented from a front facing and a side profile perspective.

FRONT VIEW

PROFILE VIEW

HEAD

The head offers several characteristics that can be observed, in addition to the previously mentioned spots from the animal's calf coat. With this anatomical region, it is possible to observe the **shape of the head and its angulation**, the presence or absence of a **white patch around the mouth**, as well as the presence or absence of **dark spots on the side of the face**.

MOUTH

Some individuals may have white at the corner of their mouth. Visualization is not always possible in monochrome photos.

DARK SPOTS ON THE FACE

Most tapirs have some kind of dark marking on their face. Some individuals may have two spots close together or widely spaced apart (a); others may have longer spots (b) or very small spots (c), and some appear to have no spots at all (d).

Usually, the spots on both sides are symmetrical.

ANGULATION

LEVEL OF RELIABILITY:
**LOW/
MEDIUM**

SCARS

It is common for tapirs to have injuries resulting from movement through dense vegetation, interactions with other tapirs or other species, or high-speed escape behavior, in which the animal may collide with obstacles in their environment.

Superficial wounds tend to disappear quickly and are therefore only temporarily useful for identification purposes. Deeper wounds, however, can become permanent scars that may remain with the individual for many years. When possible, **recording the progress of a wound** throughout the healing process provides a particularly reliable indicator for distinction between individuals.

Note: When analyzing scars, do not confuse ticks and flies with wounds!

Healing process of a wound caused by bats.

Progress of lesions that, after one year, left only small marks.

Animal with permanent scars observed for many years.

Same individual in both photos and scar can be seen under different lighting conditions.

Different scar shapes on different tapirs.

Different scar shapes on different tapirs.

Different scar shapes on different tapirs.

OTHER CHARACTERISTICS

The following are additional characteristics that, although **less frequently observed** in records, can significantly aid in the individual identification of tapirs.

Depending on the type of characteristic and the quality of the available records, this information **can act as both complementary criteria and decisive elements** in confirming the identity of a specific individual.

LEVEL OF RELIABILITY:
**MEDIUM/
HIGH**

Individual with prominent coxal tuberosity (**may be due to the animal being thin**).

Record of blindness in the left eye.

LEVEL OF RELIABILITY:
HIGH

Record of a prominent navel.

In color photos, it is possible to compare different shades of coloration in tapirs.

Monochrome record of an abscess on the lower part of the mandible. In this specific case, it was visible for about three months.

LEVEL OF
RELIABILITY:
HIGH

A reduction in the amount of muscle and fat in the animal's body can be observed (low body score).

Difference between a tapir with very little mane (A) and another with an abundant mane (B).

Different mane pattern, similar to a pattern of stripes, which we informally call a “tiger-striped” mane (A). Normal mane (B).

Records of elderly tapirs, in which a “checkered” coat pattern can be observed on the animals’ dorsal region. A whitish face is also noticeable.

Animals with coat patterns on their trunks resembling “grooves” or “folds”.

Record of a tapir with a skull deformation, giving it a “dolphin-like” appearance.

Record of a tapir with its snout cut in half.

TIPS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Some other characteristics in the records can help in identifying individuals. For example:

MOTHERS AND OFFSPRING: In general, calves remain with their mothers until approximately one and a half years of age. Thus, when two individuals are recorded together, confirmation of the calf through its spot pattern can indicate that the other animal is the mother. The inverse evaluation is also possible.

ASSOCIATIONS BETWEEN INDIVIDUALS: Although tapirs are not monogamous, it is common to observe certain “pairs” of male and female together frequently. Thus, if two animals – for example, “Maria” and “José” – often appear in association, the presence of one of them in a certain area may indicate the presence of the other. Therefore, if José is recorded together with a female, that female may be Maria, if the association is recurring.

TELEMETRY / GPS COLLARS: Animals that have previously worn a telemetry collar for monitoring often have recessed areas in their mane, which can also be used to identify them (see PAGE 26).

INTUITION AND FAMILIARITY: With good training and experience, it becomes easier to identify each individual using characteristics that are not always obvious through developing familiarity with each animal.

CHARACTERISTIC	RELIABILITY	NOTES
Sex	High	
Coat pattern of tapir calves		Depending on the observer's experience
Calf	High	
Abdomen	High	
Legs	High	
Posterior pelvic region	High	
Chest	Medium	Depends on the photo quality and angle
Face	Low	Difficult to see
Ears	High	When visible
Markings on ears	High	
Tail	Medium/High	Depends on the camera height, angle, and specific characteristics of the tail
Head		
White mouth	Low	Black and white photos are difficult to see, and often the animal's mouth is dirty
Spots on face	Low/Medium	Depends on the photo quality and angle
Angulation	Low/Medium	Depends on the trait's uniqueness and angle at which the animal appears
Scars	Medium/High	Depending on the observer's experience, the time frame of information collected, and the uniqueness of the characteristic
Other		
Prominence of coxal tuberosity	Medium/High	Depends on the angle and specific characteristics of the individual
Blindness	High	However, we have a case of an animal that had an opaque eye for 2 months and then returned to normal
Navel	Medium	Depends on the angle and specific characteristics of the individual
Coloration	Medium	Depends on the photo and whether the animal is clean
Abscess	High	Depending on the observer's experience
Body score	Medium	Depending on the time frame of information collected
Mane	Medium	Depends on the angle and specific characteristics of the individual
"Tiger-striped" mane	Low	Depends on the angle and specific characteristics of the individual
Checkered stretch marks	Low	Depends on the angle and photo quality
Deformities	High	

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